

1 **06.06.2025, Sorbonne**

2 **Interviewee: Thibaud Harrois**

3 **Interviewer: Filippo Martini**

4 **S01:** Okay, so I would like you to state your name.

5 **S00:** My name is Thibaud Harrois. I'm a lecturer in British politics at the
6 Université Sorbonne Nouvelle.

7 **S01:** Okay, and do you agree to being recorded?

8 **S00:** Yes, I agree.

9 **S01:** Thank you very much. And do you agree on the analysis, and on what I
10 told you about the fact that we're going to process data for qualitative
11 analysis?

12 **S00:** Yes.

13 **S01:** We are going to describe it, and I'm going to send it to you for your
14 revision.

15 **S00:** Very good.

16 **S01:** Thank you very much. So, let's start. First of all, I would like you
17 to introduce yourself a little bit, tell what you are doing, and what your
18 role is regarding negotiation.

19 **S00:** Well, as I said earlier, I'm a senior lecturer in British politics at
20 the Sorbonne Nouvelle, so my focus is really on analyzing what is
21 happening
22 in the relationship between the UK and the EU. I started to be interested
23 in negotiations mainly because I studied the Brexit debate in the UK, and
24 how it then evolved with the negotiations with the EU.

24 What I find particularly interesting about this example is the fact that
25 there are different levels of negotiations: within the British government
26 itself, between the British government and other actors in British politics,
27 and, of course, between the British government and the EU. There was also
28 a tentative approach to negotiate separately with the EU-27, which did not
29 work out, but there was this attempt. These different levels of
30 negotiations were particularly interesting to me.

31 Now I'm looking at the issue of trust, and how trust was lost during the
32 Brexit negotiations, and how the UK government might try to rebuild trust
33 now, trying to, as they say, reset the relationship with the EU, and what
34 that might mean.

35 My contention at first was that they were using the language of trust
36 because they wanted to rebuild trust. Now I'm a bit more skeptical about it,
37 and I still have to clarify the actual definition of trust that we can
38 find. But still, what I think is interesting is that, despite of the use of
39 the language of trust, the relationship the UK government is trying to
40 build with the EU is still a very transactional one, and that seems hard to
41 reconcile with a trustworthy attitude. The EU itself is quite skeptical

42 about the UK's approach. So, despite the use of the language of
43 trust—saying we're rebuilding that friendship or trying to soften the
44 relationship between the two parties—it remains a very complex
relationship.

45 **S01:** It's interesting, from my personal point of view. I thought it was a
46 historical event, a truly historical event. Maybe, from my point of view,
47 we didn't realize how big it was—Brexit. And I thought that studying it was
48 an amazing opportunity to really understand a lot, to have a great point of
49 view on what happened. Because it's an amazing thing—you know, we
usually
50 see creation, but not disruption, in real time, from a certain point of
51 view.

52 **S00:** Yeah. You mean what happened?

53 **S01:** Yeah, what happened, and also the consequences.

54 **S00:** Yeah. Well, Brexit is a long process, really. It started way before
55 the referendum was organized, because the UK, even when it was a full
56 member and not even discussing leaving the EU, had opt-outs and
negotiated
57 forms of differentiated integration. It did not take part in every single
58 policy implemented by the EU.

59 Then, the idea of leaving started to grow because of the pressure from
UKIP,
60 a single-issue party created mainly to put pressure on the government. But
61 also, inside the Conservative Party, part of the Conservatives were
62 Eurosceptic. That sentiment grew throughout the 1990s and progressively
up
63 until 2013, when David Cameron, who was Prime Minister at the time,
64 announced that if the Conservatives won the 2015 general election in the
UK,
65 they would organize an in-out referendum. And that's what they did. They
66 won the election in 2015 and started organizing the referendum.

67 There were many debates on whether to leave. And I think part of the
people
68 who wanted to leave never thought they were going to win the argument.
And,
69 well, the rest is history. But then again, Brexit didn't just happen on the
70 23rd of June 2016, the day people voted. At the time, we didn't know what
71 to do with the referendum results. There was this long period of first
72 trying to see how to trigger Article 50—how to leave, or actually declare
73 they wanted to leave—and then how to negotiate.

74 This had to be created from scratch, because there was no precedent for it.
75 And so, there was first a Withdrawal Agreement, then the negotiation of the
76 new relationship—the TCA, the Trade and Cooperation Agreement.

77 In 2020 and 2021, with those two agreements, we can say that Britain
78 actually left the EU and established a new relationship as a third country.
79 Except I don't think this was the end of Brexit either, because we can see,
80 with what happened in May 2025 at the summit that took place last month,

81 that Brexit is actually still going on. There are still negotiations, and
82 the May summit was about announcing new ones, so we're reopening things.

83 That shows that Brexit is definitely not a point in history—it's a long
84 historical process. It will take time. And the relationship with the EU—the
85 UK's relationship with the EU—will be marked by this event, that referendum.

86 But still, it's not a past thing; it's very much an ongoing negotiation.

87 **S01:** That's why I find it also fascinating—the fact that it didn't end, it
88 just started. Moving on, and at the same time continuing on this point,
89 because the next question is about the systematic shifts—the changes
90 happening in economics, in information. We are living through not just
91 climate change, but also war, and other transformations. What do you think,
92 in your area, which is negotiation in general but specifically what you are
93 looking at—Brexit and this kind of negotiation—what do you think has the
94 greatest impact? Which of these shifts has had the greatest impact, in your
95 point of view,

96 **S02:** On UK–EU relations?

97 **S01:** In general and in your area.

..1.1. Geopolitical

98 **S00:** Well, in recent years, definitely the war in Ukraine was a big shift
99 in the relationship between the UK and the EU, and in the way they talk to
100 each other. The necessity of finding a new relationship, I think, became
101 even more urgent because of the war in Ukraine. I think the government
102 quickly realized that, for instance, for economic reasons, they needed to
103 get closer to the EU.

..1.1. Geopolitical

104 But it was hard to make that point when the government was still headed by
105 people who were very staunch Brexiteers. After February 2022, and the
106 full-scale invasion of Ukraine, it became even more urgent to find a new
107 relationship with the EU for security reasons. It became impossible to
108 argue that the UK was now an independent state and didn't care about
109 what was happening on the continent. Quite the contrary—the UK led an effort to
110 support Ukraine, and they saw that the EU was going in exactly the same
111 direction. They started to talk to each other about sanctions against
112 Russia, and then expanded this cooperation.

113 **S01:** So it was maybe an accelerator, in a certain point of view.

114 **S00:** Yes.

115 **S01:** And what do you think—moving to the next question—what is the most
116 demanding negotiation you have had the chance to observe or study?

117 **S00:** Unfortunately, I've never observed negotiations directly.

118 **S01:** Of course.

119 **S00:** But I've studied Brexit, and that's definitely the negotiation I've
120 followed most closely. Within Brexit, there were also different internal
121 negotiations—if you look at what happened with the Northern Ireland
122 Protocol, or the Windsor Agreement, and now the idea of a reset. These are

123 different negotiations that took place within the broader framework of
124 Brexit, and that's what I'm interested in.

125 **S01:** Okay. What do you think makes these negotiations more demanding,
126 more complicated?

127 **S00:** What makes them complex? Well, first, one thing that makes it
128 complex is that the UK used to be a member state. The people who negotiated
129 Brexit knew the EU very well, and thought they could find a way to turn things to
130 their advantage—to negotiate in a way that would make the EU ready to
131 accept what they expected it to do. That's why they started negotiating
132 with member states rather than with the Commission, or at both levels at
133 the same time.

..3.1.1. Challenges

134 And of course, the other way around, it's very hard to negotiate with the
135 UK, because people had an idea of what the UK used to be as a partner
136 within the EU, and they definitely didn't want to make any concession to
137 the UK, which was setting an example, or precedent, for leaving. This
138 reinforced the EU's attitude: we need to be ready to say no to whatever
139 strikes us as an exception or something we wouldn't offer to other member
140 states.

..3.1.1. Challenges

141 For instance, cherry-picking—this was something the EU kept repeating at
142 the time. The UK couldn't choose to be part of some freedoms of the single
143 market and not go for of them. This was really part of the complexity of
144 the process.

145 **S01:** Well, I remember you were talking in your panel about these two
146 aspects, when you summarized that idea of a friend that became foes, to
147 simplify it in a certain way. That's why I like this kind of discussion
148 about Brexit, because it brings up many different layers that are useful to
149 consider for different aspects of negotiation. It happens often that a
150 partnership breaks up, and you have to negotiate with a partner you know
151 very well. You can also try to leverage your knowledge about the other side.
152 So I think it could also be applied to other fields.

..3.1.1. Challenges

153 And coming back to Europe, what do you think about the conference? We
154 are trying here to build bridges between the academic world and the
155 practitioner world, and there is a well-known gap between them. Everyone
156 talks about it. What do you think about this gap between the academic
157 world and practitioners, especially in negotiation in the field?

158 **S00:** I think it's the same everywhere. Whenever there are people like
159 political scientists or international-relations scholars studying what's
160 happening in the world, and others who actually do these things, it's quite
161 difficult for them to talk to each other. Academics have a tendency to
162 conceptualize things, to fit them into predetermined theories, and to look
163 at how things take shape and how logical they are. Practitioners don't have
164 time to think in that way; they act as things happen. So sometimes it may

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seem disconnected when academics try to conceptualize and explain something that practitioners simply do.

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It's hard to reconcile the two, but I think what's important—and what this conference is trying to achieve, which I find a very good ambition—is to have these people actually talk to each other. Academics can say, "Look, you're doing what we, in theory, conceptualized," and practitioners can realize that they can step back, take some time to think about what they did—often without realizing it—in order to improve their practice and learn from those who have time to think, when they don't because they are working on the ground.

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S01: It's a negotiation between two worlds.

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S00: Yes, exactly. Or a meeting, at least.

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S01: Okay. Coming back to the European part of the conference, do you think

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that in Europe we have a systematic or different way to negotiate compared to other regions?

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S00: I'm not sure, because I don't know the other regions that well, so I'm only guessing. But I think that because of the EU, the culture of negotiation has developed in Europe in a way that may not exist elsewhere. We constantly have to think about the fact that there are 26 other partners in the EU, and that what we want is not necessarily what everyone wants. That may be part of our political culture, even if politicians don't constantly talk about the EU and often try to avoid politicizing it by saying, "This is what we're doing at the EU level." Too often, the EU is seen as something abstract, and we don't talk about the concrete way things happen at the EU level.

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Maybe we have this culture more present in Europe now. However, one has to

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realize—and as a French person, I know this well—that negotiation is almost absent from our political culture. We don't know how to negotiate politically between different parties. We're very bad at building coalitions, when you would think that, being grown-ups, people with the best interests of France in mind would be able to negotiate and compromise.

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S01: You're talking to an Italian, so we could impart lesson about that...

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S00: Other countries, like Germany, have constitutions that force them to negotiate, and this might be positive. It gives them greater awareness of the necessity to negotiate and be ready to make compromises.

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S01: Yes, let's see what happens in the future. For now, I think one thing we have in common in Europe is the absence of the ability for internal negotiation, from a certain point of view. Going on, what do you think could be a key skill for negotiation in the future? What kind of skill should we teach to negotiators?

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..5.1. Essential Skills a

..5.1. Essential Skill:

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S00: Maybe one thing that is sometimes missing in negotiations—although

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I suppose it's part of the theory and some practitioners already know it—is

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understanding better the culture of those you're talking to. Some

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mistakes—going back to the Brexit example—were made both in the UK and in

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the EU because the UK thought it knew how to talk to the EU when in fact

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they didn't. They believed they could use their own framework, when in fact

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the EU had a different approach. Having a transactional approach, treating

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everything as economic, led the UK to make many mistakes, while the EU was

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talking more politically than economically. So cultural differences are

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important to keep in mind to adapt negotiating skills.

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S01: Thank you very much. Well, we're going towards the end, so one of the

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last questions: do you think there could be a research question that

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academics should address to better understand negotiation?

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S00: A good research question... Well, I work on trust, and I think—although

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I'm already trying to answer it—looking at trust in negotiations is

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essential. It's not new, I'm not trying to invent something, but it's part

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of the equation when trying to understand why negotiations sometimes can't

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take place or fail. Paradoxically, some assume that if you adopt an

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attitude that is hard to understand or surprising, you might gain an

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advantage. I think on the contrary: this often leads to mistakes and failed

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negotiations. So the question of trust and the attitude linked with it—how

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you demonstrate or signal trust—is important to study.

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S01: The last question, something lighter: what about a book or a movie on

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negotiation that you would like to suggest?

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S00: On Brexit negotiations, there's a very good documentary— *L'Europe au*

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pied du mur: ([https://campus.arte.](https://campus.arte.tv/program/brexit-l-europe-au-pied-du-mur)

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[tv/program/brexit-l-europe-au-pied-du-mur](https://campus.arte.tv/program/brexit-l-europe-au-pied-du-mur)). It follows Michel Barnier

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during the Brexit negotiations. It was made by Alain de Halleux, who works

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with Arte, and released in 2019. I think it's quite good because it shows

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what the EU negotiating team went through during the process.

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S01: Thank you very much.

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S00: I'll send you the title because it's in French—*L'Europe au pied du mur*.

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S01: Yes, I will see. Thank you very much. And the last thing: a book?

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S00: If we stay in the same field, I'd recommend *Inside the Deal: How the*

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EU got Brexit done, by Stefaan De Rynck, an EU official who was Senior

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Advisor to EU Chief Negotiator Michel Barnier on Brexit matters.

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S01: If you don't have it now, it's a good reason to stay in touch.

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S00: Yes, exactly.

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S01: So I'll wait for your message about it.

244 | **S00:** Okay.

245 | **S01:** Thank you very much.

246 | **S00:** My pleasure.

247 | **S01:** Thank you very much. I really appreciate that you found the time for
248 | this interview.